

Complexation equilibria of succinylsulfathiazole with VO^{II}, UO₂^{II}, Cu^{II}, Ni^{II} and Mn^{II}

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Abstract : The proton-ligand stability constants ($\log K_1^H$, $\log K_2^H$) of succinylsulfathiazole (SSTZ) and stepwise stability constants ($\log K_1$, $\log K_2$) of its complexes with VO^{II}, UO₂^{II}, Cu^{II}, Ni^{II} and Mn^{II} have been determined potentiometrically in *N,N'*-dimethylformamide (DMF)-water and dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO)-water systems [25 : 75 and 50 : 50 (% v/v)] at 25 ± 0.1 °C and 0.15 M (NaClO₄) ionic strength. The values of $\log K_1^H$ and $\log K_2^H$ as well as $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ increase with the increasing DMF or DMSO concentrations. The stability order of the complexes have been found to be VO^{II} > UO₂^{II} > Cu^{II} > Ni^{II} > Mn^{II}.

Keywords : Succinylsulfathiazole, stability constants, bivalent metal complexes, aqueous-organic solvents.

Sulfonamides and its *N*¹ and *N*⁴ substituted derivatives are well known sulfa drugs¹. Succinylsulfathiazole {2-[*N*-(4)-succinylsulfanilamidothiazole]} (SSTZ), for example, has a broad spectrum of bacteriostatic activity affecting gram +ve, gram -ve and many protozoan organisms². It is commonly used for intestinal infections and pre-surgical sterilization of gut³. Metal complexes of sulfa drugs play a vital role in metabolic and toxicological function in biological systems⁴.

The present studies have been carried out on complexation equilibria of SSTZ with proton and different metal ions in aqueous-DMF and aqueous-DMSO mixtures at 25 ± 0.1 °C and 0.15 M ionic strength using potentiometric technique⁵.

Results and discussion

Succinylsulfathiazole has two potentially ionizable functional groups. It acts as a biprotic acid and offers two well separated buffer regions in the pH range (3.0–9.0) due to successive deprotonation of -COOH (1 ⇌ 2) and -SO₂NH (2 ⇌ 3) moieties (Scheme 1). Since -COOH group is a stronger acidic group than the -SO₂NH- group, the first ionization constant pK_{a1} corresponds to the dissociation of a proton from the carboxylic group and pK_{a2} corresponds to the dissociation of proton from nitrogen in sulfonamide group.

Scheme 1. Ionization equilibria of succinylsulfathiazole : [1, SSTZ; 2, SSTZ⁻; 3, SSTZ²⁻].

The present pK_{a1} ($\log K_2^H$) values lying between 4.8–5.7 for -COOH group in case of SSTZ are in agreement with corresponding acids [butanoic acid (4.82) and propanoic acid (4.88)] reported earlier⁶. The pK_a values of some sulfa drugs namely sulfanilamide (10.05), sulfapyridine (9.60), sulfadiazine (7.38) and sulfathiazole (7.89) have been reported. The pK_{a2} ($\log K_1^H$) values for succinylsulfathiazole in different aqueous-organic media in the range of 7 to 8 (Table 1) lie close to its related ligand (sulfathiazole).

The proton-ligand stability constants of succinylsulfathiazole (Table 1) increase (SSTZ becomes less acidic) with the increasing concentrations of organic solvents (DMF/DMSO) in aquo-organic mixture. Here, it should

Table 1. Proton-ligand stability constants of succinylsulfathiazole and metal-ligand stability constants of its complexes in DMSO : H₂O and DMF : H₂O (25 : 75 and 50 : 50 % v/v) mixtures at 25 ± 0.1 °C and 0.15 M ionic strength

DMSO : H ₂ O :: 25 : 75 (% v/v)				DMSO : H ₂ O :: 50 : 50 (% v/v)		
Cation	log K ₁ ^H (pK _{a2})	log K ₂ ^H (pK _{a1})	log β ₂ ^H	log K ₁ ^H (pK _{a2})	log K ₂ ^H (pK _{a1})	log β ₂ ^H
H ⁺	7.14	4.85	11.95	7.51	5.26	12.77
pH range	5.2–8.5	3.0–6.6		5.5–9.0	3.2–7.2	
	log K ₁	log K ₂	log β ₂	log K ₁	log K ₂	log β ₂
VO ^{II}	4.78	3.96	8.74	6.35	5.25	11.60
UO ₂ ^{II}	4.15	3.28	7.43	5.81	4.47	10.28
Cu ^{II}	3.40	2.87	6.27	4.61	4.01	8.62
Ni ^{II}	3.04	2.72	5.76	3.19	3.06	6.25
Mn ^{II}	2.93	2.51	5.44	3.13	2.90	6.03
DMF : H ₂ O :: 25 : 75 (% v/v)				DMF : H ₂ O :: 50 : 50 (% v/v)		
Cation	log K ₁ ^H (pK _{a2})	log K ₂ ^H (pK _{a1})	log β ₂ ^H	log K ₁ ^H (pK _{a2})	log K ₂ ^H (pK _{a1})	log β ₂ ^H
H ⁺	7.67	4.90	12.57	8.01	5.62	13.63
pH range	5.6–8.8	3.4–7.0		6.0–9.0	3.8–7.6	
	log K ₁	log K ₂	log β ₂	log K ₁	log K ₂	log β ₂
VO ^{II}	5.59	4.05	9.64	6.24	4.68	10.92
UO ₂ ^{II}	4.89	3.6	8.49	5.77	4.11	9.88
Cu ^{II}	4.56	3.41	7.97	4.97	3.63	8.60
Ni ^{II}	3.23	2.82	6.05	3.80	2.93	6.63
Mn ^{II}	3.06	2.67	5.73	3.12	2.79	5.93

be noted that as predicted by Born equation, the creation of charge in media of low dielectric constants is an unfavorable process, hence, resulting in higher pK_a values, which were higher in 50 : 50 (% v/v) mixture in comparison to 25 : 75 (% v/v) mixtures. While comparing the pK_a values, for the same (% v/v) composition, in different solvent water mixtures the sequence DMF-H₂O > DMSO-H₂O was observed.

an acid solvent conjugate base conjugate acid

Ionization of an SSTZ produces ions. The conjugate acid from the solvent is a cation that is stabilized by association with other solvent molecules, a phenomenon called solvation. The conjugate base of the acid is an anion that in most cases is also stabilized by solvation. In the present investigations, SSTZ behaves as stronger acid in DMSO-water mixture (lower pK_a values) in comparison to DMF-water mixture. This can be explained on the basis of higher dielectric constant (ε) of DMSO-H₂O [ε = 71.80 for 25 : 75 (% v/v), ε = 63.60 for 50 : 50 (% v/v)] as compared to DMF-H₂O [ε = 69.58 for 25 : 75 (% v/v), ε = 59.15 for 50 : 50 (% v/v)] system since solvents

having large dielectric constants favour charge formation and separation. The enhancing proton solvation properties of DMSO as compared to DMF also account for lower pK_a values in DMSO⁷.

The \bar{n} values were calculated in the pH range 4.0–5.8, 4.5–6.2, 5.0–6.8, 5.8–7.5 and 6.2–7.8 for VO^{II}, UO₂^{II}, Cu^{II}, Ni^{II} and Mn^{II} respectively and lie in the range 0–2 in each case, thereby, indicating the formation of 1 : 1 (ML) and 1 : 2 (ML₂) complexes. The values of metal-ligand stability constants (log K₁ and log K₂, Table 1) are greater in 50 : 50 (% v/v) as compared to 25 : 75 (% v/v) in both solvent systems. This suggests that coordinate bond formed between metal and ligand has more covalent character in case of 50 : 50 (% v/v) having lower dielectric constant. Higher log β₂ values were observed in DMF-H₂O 25 : 75 (% v/v) as compared to DMSO-H₂O 25 : 75 (% v/v) mixture for each cation used since SSTZ behaves as more basic ligand (greater pK_a values) in DMF-water mixture.

The stability constants of the complexes follow the order VO^{II} > UO₂^{II} > Cu^{II} > Ni^{II} > Mn^{II} which is just the reverse of the order of the cation radii and is in agree-

ment with the Irving-Williams order of stability⁸. Among oxo cations, the higher stability of VO^{II} complexes may be attributed to the participation of 3d orbitals in coordination in contrast to behavior of 5f orbitals in UO₂^{II}. It is well known that VO^{II} and UO₂^{II} are hard metal ions while Cu^{II}, Ni^{II} and Mn^{II} are borderline metal ions. The potential donor sites on ligand (SSTZ) are O and N atoms and thus are hard donor sites. The favorable interactions between hard metal ions and hard ligand further account for greater stability of VO^{II} and UO₂^{II} as compared to borderline metal ions.

Experimental

All the reagents used were of A.R. grade. Succinyl-sulfathiazole was procured from Sigma and its solution was prepared in DMF/DMSO. A digital pH-meter Model pH 5652A (Electronics Corporation of India Ltd.) with a glass and calomel electrodes assembly, reading up to 0.01 units, was used to follow the change in pH during the titrations. A thermostated titration vessel of 20 ml capacity was used. The electrode system was calibrated using standard buffer solutions of pH 4.00 and 7.00.

For pH titrations, the following thermostated solutions were titrated against carbonate free 0.1 M NaOH solutions.

(A) DMF/DMSO : H₂O :: 25 : 75 (% v/v)

(a) 2 ml 0.1 M HClO₄ + 2 ml 1.5 M NaClO₄ + 5 ml DMF/DMSO + 11 ml H₂O

(b) 2 ml 0.1 M HClO₄ + 2 ml 1.5 M NaClO₄ + 2 ml 0.02 M SSTZ + 3 ml DMF/DMSO + 11 ml H₂O

(c) 2 ml 0.1 M HClO₄ + 2 ml 1.5 M NaClO₄ + 2 ml 0.02 M SSTZ + 2 ml 0.01 M metal ion solution + 3 ml DMF/DMSO + 9 ml H₂O

(B) DMF/DMSO : H₂O :: 50 : 50 (% v/v)

(a) 2 ml 0.1 M HClO₄ + 2 ml 1.5 M NaClO₄ + 10 ml

DMF/DMSO + 6 ml H₂O

(b) 2 ml 0.1 M HClO₄ + 2 ml 1.5 M NaClO₄ + 2 ml 0.02 M SSTZ + 8 ml DMF/DMSO + 6 ml H₂O

(c) 2 ml 0.1 M HClO₄ + 2 ml 1.5 M NaClO₄ + 2 ml 0.02 M SSTZ + 2 ml 0.01 M metal ion solution + 8 ml DMF/DMSO + 4 ml H₂O

The ionic strength (0.15 M) was adjusted by adding calculated amount of 1.5 M NaClO₄ and the total initial volume of the solution were kept 20 ml by adding appropriate quantity of double distilled water and DMF/DMSO. The plots of pH values against volume of NaOH added were drawn. The values of \bar{n}_A , \bar{n} and pL were calculated using the Irving-Rossotti method⁵. The proton-ligand stability constants (log K₁^H and log K₂^H) and metal-ligand stability constants (log K₁ and log K₂) were calculated⁵.

References

- 1 P G Streeher, "The Merck Index of Chemicals and Drugs", Merck and Co Inc Rahway, New Jersey, USA, 1960, p 992
- 2 A Burger, "Medicinal Chemistry", Wiley Interscience, New York, 1997
- 3 G Patrick, "Medicinal Chemistry", Viva BPL, New Delhi, 2002, p 255
- 4 G A Oarter and R L Wain, *Ann Appl Biol*, 1964, **23**, 291
- 5 H M Irving and H S Rossotti, *J Chem Soc*, 1953, 3397, 1954, 2904
- 6 "Vogel's Text Book of Quantitative Chemical Analysis", eds J Bassett, R C Denny, G H Jeffery and J Menoham, Longman, 5th ed., ELBS, London, 1989
- 7 K K Saxena, S Sharma and R S Saxena, *Afinidad*, 1985, **42**, 91, H. A Azab, A M El-Nady and M S Saleh, *Monatsh Chem*, 1994, **125**, 233, A Boraee and N Mohamed, *Ann Chim.*, 2002, **92**, 575.
- 8 H Irving and R J P William, *Nature*, 1948, **162**, 746, *J Chem Soc.*, 1953, 3192